

PARENTING STYLES AND SCHOOL ADJUSTMENT OF JUNIOR SECONDARY ONE STUDENTS IN ETICHE, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the parenting styles and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the 5,542 junior secondary One (JS 1) students in the twenty-five public secondary schools in the study area. A sample size of 450 respondents was selected for the study using the multi-stage sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire titled “Parenting Styles and School Adjustment of Students Questionnaire (PSSASQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was face-validated, while its reliability was determined using Cronbach alpha, resulting in an overall reliability coefficient of 0.71. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics was used for data analysis. The results showed, among others, that authoritative parenting style was positively and significantly related to the school adjustment of junior secondary one students. Based on the findings, relevant recommendations were made, among which is that parents should preferably adopt an authoritative parenting style in training their children so that they can establish peaceful relationships with others and display conducts that will help them in their day-to-day activities while in school.

Keywords: parenting, styles, school, adjustment, students

Introduction

The transition from primary to secondary school could be very challenging in the development of young boys and girls, and as such, some students may not be

adequately prepared for the psychosocial realities of secondary education. Students enter secondary schools with diverse backgrounds and it is not an exaggeration to say that some students come from homes, primary schools, and communities where violence, stealing, cheating, bullying, deceit, lies, infractions, disrespect, pilfering, fighting, fraud, examination malpractice, and other unruly behaviours are common. Others come from homes, primary schools, and communities where pro-social behaviours such as obedience, kindness, love, mutuality, respect for elders or constituted authorities, and other standard social values and norms are held in high esteem.

In secondary school, the expectation is that students should be law-abiding, obedient to teachers and school authorities, show respect to fellow students and teachers, shun lies, stealing, destruction of students and schools' property, fighting, cheating, and examination malpractices. Besides, they are expected to copy the notes, study hard, and do their assignments and homework. They must develop a positive attitude towards school and obey its rules and regulations. These are necessary for optimum academic activities and achievement. It is when students have discarded antisocial behaviours and adopted pro-social behaviours based on mutual respect for one another, essential for a warm relationship among teachers and students and for academic activities to thrive, that the students are regarded as having adjusted to the school (Ukaegbu & Obikoya, 2017).

Parenting styles, on the other hand, are standard strategies that parents use in their childrearing. It entails how parents respond to their children's demands and nurture them with care and affection so that they can maintain positive social adjustment. Parenting adolescents for overall adjustment is one of the most essential tasks required of parents in nurturing children, particularly in the 21st century. This is because many children are gaining new knowledge and experiences due to the prevailing technological and sociological changes in society. No wonder Sarwar (2016) averred that proper parenting style is necessary, particularly in this recent time where adolescents are exposed to activities and information from people that challenge their personal ideologies, family standards, and values.

With the impact of the aforementioned influences in society, it is expected that the family, as the first socialisation agent, should nurture children in such a way that they can effectively adjust their behaviour to fit with societal demands. Huppert et al. (2010) argued that parents have an important role in educating their children with sound moral principles and standards of behaviour that will guide their conduct in life. Shannon and Sarah (2015) stated that the family lays the foundation of education before the child goes to school, and the personality that the child takes to school is determined by the home. This makes it imperative for parents to nurture healthy relationships in children, as these relationships lay the foundation for the child's personality, life choices, and overall behaviour.

One of the parenting styles that may likely influence students' school adjustment is the authoritative parenting style. According to Ukaegbu and Edem (2021), in an authoritative parenting style, both parents and children take joint decisions after sharing their views. Moreover, Oliveira et al. (2014) posited that an authoritative parenting style puts responsibility on the child by permitting him or her to choose, which gives the child the impetus to develop the qualities of self-discipline and cooperation. Authoritative parenting is characterised by joint decision-making, mutual respect, autonomy, and responsibility. All members of an authoritative family have a voice when making family decisions. Kordi and Baharudin (2013) maintained that in an authoritative home, parents treat their children as equal with respect and dignity. An authoritative parenting approach allows children to have their own ideas and preferences, as well as the right to make their own decisions when appropriate. Authoritative parenting is characterised by an optimum balance of responsiveness. Authoritative parents are responsive to their children and actively listen to their questions. When children fail to meet expectations, these parents are more forgiving and nurturing than punishing. Ansumwi and Jeemina (2021) observed that parents from authoritative homes usually monitor and set clear standards for their children's conduct. They are assertive but not intrusive or restrictive. Their disciplinary methods are supportive rather than punitive. They want their children to be assertive, socially responsible, self-regulated, and cooperative.

Adegboyega et al. (2017) revealed that students from authoritative homes usually score higher in academic and school adjustment, as they always respect the dignity of other persons in the school, obey the rules of the school, and give room for other schoolmates to speak their minds without reacting aggressively. This means that the display of an authoritative style of parent-child relationship could likely help students adjust to numerous academic demands in the school while behaving peacefully in meeting the tasks of social relationships. Academically, Femi (2018) found that students from authoritative homes are most likely to perform better than children from autocratic parents. This is because their parents are often involved in their school work and they allow the children to express their feelings, needs, and demands without any threat. Mensah and Kuranchie (2013) found in one of their empirical studies that children of authoritative parenting whose parents were warm and accepting were often seen to engage in socially accepted behaviours and perform academically better than children of autocratic parents. This means that authoritative parenting has significant roles to play in students' social adjustment in terms of behaviour and performance, unlike autocratic parenting, which promotes unsocial, rebellious, and dependent children who are prone to withdrawal from school.

Another parenting style of interest in this study is the authoritarian style. Njoku and Akaninwor-David (2019) see authoritarian parenting as a rigid and strict pattern of rearing children. Parents who practice an authoritarian parenting style have a strict set of rules in place to enforce compliance. No explanation is provided to the child for

any punishment received. When any attempt is made to question the parents' authority, the only response provided is "because I said so." Vijila et al. (2013) noted that children from these homes are found to be less cheerful and display more aggressive tendencies. According to Mensah and Kuranchie (2013), this parenting pattern is restrictive and involves the establishment of many rules for the child, with a demand for strict obedience. Parents who adopt this parenting style use force rather than obedience to enforce rules. Children from this home are expected to accept their parents' opinions of right and wrong without questioning them. Children from such homes are often obedient and display a high level of self-control, but have been shown to be emotionally withdrawn and lacking in curiosity.

Adegboyega et al. (2021) added that authoritarian parenting has a negative influence on students' social adjustment in secondary schools. As a result, poor social relationships may lead to poor academic adjustment among students.

Permissive parenting style is the third variable that could influence the academic adjustment of students. It is a type of parenting style characterised by low demands and high responsiveness. Such a style of parenting may have a severe impact on students' social adjustment. Permissive parents tend to be very loving, yet they provide few guidelines and values. According to Seth and Emmanuel (2018), these parents do not expect mature behaviour from their children and often seem more like a friend than a parental figure. Due to such a carefree life, students from such homes are less aware of the limits of acceptable behaviour. They are most likely to behave the way they want, without minding whether such behaviour is unhealthy. Students from permissive parents are usually unable to manage their impulses; hence, they find it difficult to adjust their behaviour to agree with the acceptable moral norms of the school.

In a permissive parenting style, parents make little demands from their children as regards appropriate behaviour and make little attempt to control their behaviour. Permissive parents permit their children to act as they please. Little or no attempt is made to control the behaviour of children by parents with a permissive parenting style. According to Elias and Yee (2019), permissive parents are characterised by non-controlling, non-demanding behaviour towards their children's behaviour and make little demands on appropriate behaviour from their children. Permissive parents believe that children have rights similar to those of adults but expect them not to be responsible in character and behaviour. Rules are seldom enforced, if they are made at all. Heaven and Ciarrochi (2015) argued that this form of parenting leads to immature adulthood, where the individual acts with little regard for socially appropriate behaviour.

Permissive parenting is characterised by low expectations of maturity and control. Permissive parents believe that when children are controlled or disciplined, it inhibits

their natural psychological growth or self-actualizing tendency. Due to such beliefs, permissive parents view themselves as resources to be used by the child without taking active roles in the child's choice or moulding them in ways that are socially appropriate.

Seth and Emmanuel (2018) conducted a study on the role of permissive and neglectful parenting styles in determining the academic performance of adolescents in the senior high schools in the Birim Municipality. The authors found a significant difference in adolescents' social adjustment based on permissive parenting and other parenting styles. The authors added that in permissive homes, children are not properly nurtured in moral attitudes and habits, and they are not always cautioned when they go wrong. They and their parents tend to live a carefree life, which is detrimental to academic adjustment. Njoku and Akaninwor-David (2019) added that permissive parenting is the main cause of disruptive behaviours among students in public secondary schools.

Thus, this present study was carried out to investigate the extent to which authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting styles impact the school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The researchers believe that carrying out this study would be very beneficial to parents, students, and school administrators and government at all levels, given the enormous role played by these organisations in shaping the behaviour of children.

Statement of the Problem

It is common to read, hear, or witness instances of students' involvement in anti-social behaviours such as indiscipline in schools, child abuse, alcohol intake, drug abuse, rape, prostitution, sexual perversion, stealing, cultism, adolescent suicide, school dropout, and all kinds of wanton misdemeanours. It is unfortunate that some of these social problems are caused by students who are unable to cope academically.

Many have agreed that deviant acts perpetrated by students in secondary schools are responsible for the downward turn in the academic performance of these students. To the knowledge of the researchers, it is not certain whether efforts taken by parents, researchers, teachers, school administrators, and other stakeholders at linking behaviours among secondary school students to social problems with a view to curbing these behaviours have yielded more positive fruits in the past. In light of the overall challenges of school adjustment, the present study sought to investigate the connection between parenting styles and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between parenting styles and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the relationship between authoritative parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students;
2. Investigate the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students;
3. Ascertain the relationship between permissive parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between authoritative parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students?
2. What is the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students?
3. What is the relationship between permissive parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students.
2. There is no significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students.
3. There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two theories, namely, the Parental Attachment Theory proposed by John Bowlby and the Stage-Environment Fit Theory propounded by Eccles and Midgley. They are discussed below.

Parental Attachment Theory

Parental Attachment Theory was proposed by John Bowlby in 1980. The theory states that the best way to ensure that there is secure attachment necessary to create emotionally healthy children is for the child to be looked after by one constant caregiver, preferably the mother, who is always in close proximity and responsive to the needs of the child. Bowlby said that constant care provided by a loving parent during childhood benefits them in the long-term, and such care could be, but not limited to,

child bonding, breastfeeding, baby-weaning, guidance, and bed-sharing. This is because infants have a tendency to seek closeness to another person and feel secure when that person is present.

According to the theorist, the parent/child relationship forms the basis of the child's experience and attitude towards people in later years, and it strengthens or weakens the child's innate endowments and temperament. In this context, sensitive and emotionally available parenting helps the child to form a secure attachment style, which fosters a child's socio-emotional development and behavioural wellbeing. Less sensitive and emotionally available parenting or neglect of the child's needs may result in insecure forms of attachment style, which is a risk to much anti-social behaviour as well as poor academic adjustment among students.

Stage-Environment Fit Theory

Stage-Environment Fit Theory was proposed by Eccles and Midgley in 1989. The theory states that the manifestation of any given behaviour or attribute depends largely on the extent of consonance between a child's existing abilities, characteristics, and interests and the opportunities afforded to him in the immediate social environment. Fit, adaptation, or adjustment is optimal when the environmental features experienced by a child are structured according to the child's recent needs and his developmental level. A dissonance in needs reflects an asynchrony or disharmony between the amount of stimulation in the environment and existing abilities or motivations.

The Stage-Environment Fit Theory is relevant to this study because it proposes that students will experience maladjustment in school if the environment of the school does not support their current developmental stage, cognitive, and emotional growth. On the other hand, students will experience adjustment when the school environment supports their current developmental stage and promotes their cognitive and emotional growth. So, the teacher has the responsibility to support the students in their quest for academic excellence. Thus, it is the congruence between the developmental trajectory and the environmental change trajectory that determines the extent of adjustment among students in the school environment.

Empirical Studies

Njoku and Akaninwor-David (2019) investigated parenting styles as correlates of social adjustment among students with physical disabilities in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. Among others, it was revealed that authoritative parenting style had a significantly higher prediction of inadequate social adjustment on the part of the students.

Olufemi (2018) investigated the influence of parenting styles and peer pressure on the social adjustment of in-school adolescents in Ibadan metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised students in senior secondary school one and two (SS 1–SS 2). The participants' ages ranged from 12 to 18 years old. 150 questionnaires were administered, out of which 149 students participated, resulting in 98% of total respondents. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire consisting of a parenting style scale, a peer pressure scale, and a social adjustment scale. The data were analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression statistics methods. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The results revealed that there was a significant relationship between the independent variables (parenting style and peer group pressure) and the dependent variable (social adjustment) in the following order of magnitude: parenting style ($r = 0.658$; $p < 0.05$) and peer pressure ($r = 0.760$; $P < 0.05$). Similarly, the result also indicated that the two independent variables (parenting style and peer group pressure), when pulled together, have a significant effect on the social adjustment of in-school adolescents in Ibadan Metropolis.

The result shows that peer pressure made the most significant contribution to the social adjustment of in-school adolescents in Ibadan Metropolis ($\beta = 0.704$), followed by parenting styles ($\beta = 0.136$). It was recommended that additional research examine the influence of peer group acceptance on the social adjustment of adolescents in the context of other potential influences, including the nature of the parent-child relationship, the academic culture in the home setting, and the support and encouragement that students receive from teachers at school.

Jackson (2016) conducted a study to establish the influence of peers on the adjustment of form-one students to secondary school. Bronfenbrenner's ecological theory was employed by the study. This study also employed an explanatory survey research design. The target population was 207 heads of schools, 207 heads of counselling departments, and 14,043 form-one students in Uasin Gishu County. Several sampling techniques were used to select the study's participants. Data collection was conducted using questionnaire sets and focus group discussions. The study used a mixed method, hence the quantitative and qualitative data. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The findings after computing the correlation and regression statistics indicated ($r = 0.459$, $\rho < 0.05$) and ($\beta = 0.459$, $p < 0.05$), respectively, for peer influence on the adjustment to secondary school. Qualitative data was analysed based on emerging themes. The findings indicate that peers have a significant influence on the adjustment of form-one students to secondary school.

Akpan-Idiok and Ackley (2018) carried out a study to determine the influence of family background on adolescent social adjustment in Southern senatorial district of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study used a sample of 448 adolescents randomly selected. Four research hypotheses were formulated for this study and tested at .05 level of significance with 348 degrees of freedom. A well-validated 23-item questionnaire was used to collect the required data. The collected data was tested using an independent t-test analysis for the hypotheses. From the analysis, the following findings were made, among others: there is a significant influence of family type on students' social development ($P > 0.05$). It was reported that family structure significantly influences students' social adjustment.

Methodology

Research Design

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. This design is used whenever a researcher wants to find out the magnitude and direction of the relationship that exists between the dependent and independent variables (Wali, 2002). Therefore, this design was considered suitable for this study because it enabled the researcher to investigate the relationship between parenting styles and school adjustment among junior secondary one students.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of all 5,542 junior secondary one (JS 1) students in twenty-five public junior secondary schools in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State (Etche Local Government Education Authority, Okehi, 2024).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 450 public junior secondary one (JS 1) students was selected for the study through a multi-stage sampling technique. To get an adequate number of schools, the balloting method of random sampling was used to select 15 public junior secondary schools out of the 25 existing schools in the study area. Thereafter, purposive sampling was used to select 30 public junior secondary one students in each of the 15 schools selected for the study, which gave a total of 450 respondents.

Instrument for Data Collection

A researcher-made questionnaire entitled “Parenting Styles and Students' School Adjustment Questionnaire (PSSSAQ)” was used for data collection. The items were raised in line with the research questions and hypotheses. The instrument had two parts: Section A, which contained 18 items, 6 items measuring each of authoritative, authoritarian and permissive parenting styles while section B contained 20 items measuring students' school adjustment. The instrument was responded to on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1, respectively. All the items were positively skewed.

Validation of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the instrument, two copies of the instrument were given to experts in Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, University of Uyo, Uyo, who made necessary corrections and also expunged items that were irrelevant to the study. All the corrections were incorporated by the researcher in the final draft.

Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, the researcher administered the questionnaire to 20 JS 1 students drawn from the population but did not participate in the final study. The data collected from their responses were analysed using the Cronbach alpha procedure. An overall reliability coefficient of 0.71 was obtained and this was high enough, making the instrument highly reliable.

Method of Data Administration

The research instrument was personally administered on the respondents in their respective schools by the researcher. Also, permission from the respective principals were sought to allow the respondents respond to the items in the instrument. In addition to items written on the questionnaire, the subjects were given verbal instructions and clarifications where necessary. Copies of the questionnaire were retrieved after completion without subjecting the respondents to time constraint. All the 330 copies of the questionnaire administered were filled properly according to instructions and collected instantly.

Method of Data Analysis

The data generated were analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics. In answering the research questions, the r-value was used to determine the magnitude or weight of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Whereas in testing the null hypotheses, the r-value was compared with .05 critical value so as to determine the significance of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

RESULTS

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation between Authoritative Parenting Style and School Adjustment of Junior Secondary One Students in Etche Local Government Area

Variables	n	r-value	p-value	Remark
Authoritative parenting (X)	450	.72	.001	Sig.
School adjustment (Y)				

p<.05

The result in Table 1 shows a correlation value of .72. This implies that there is a high positive relationship between authoritative parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students. This means that most of the students reared with authoritative parenting style are likely to be adjusted in school. However, the test of the corresponding hypothesis reveals that the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is statistically significant at .05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation between Authoritarian Parenting Style and School Adjustment of Junior Secondary One Students in Etche Local Government Area

Variables	n	r-value	p-value	Remark
Authoritarian parenting (X)	450	- .64	.753	Not Sig.
School adjustment (Y)				

p>.05

Table 2 shows a correlation value of -.64. This implies that there is a moderately negative relationship between authoritarian parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students. This means that most of the students who are reared by authoritarian parents are likely to be maladjusted in school. However, the test of the corresponding hypothesis reveals that the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is not statistically significant at .05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation between Permissive Parenting Style and School Adjustment of Junior Secondary One Students in Etche Local Government Area

Variables	n	r-value	p-value	Remark
Permissive parenting (X)	450	-.54	1.32	Not Sig.
School adjustment (Y)				

p>.05

The data in Table 3 shows a correlation value of -.54. This implies that there is a moderately negative relationship between permissive parenting style and School adjustment of junior secondary one students. The negative relationship means that most students who are reared by permissive parents are likely to be maladjusted in school. However, the test of the corresponding hypothesis reveals that the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is not statistically

significant at .05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of data on research question one and hypothesis one revealed a high positive and significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area. The fact that authoritative parenting affords parents the privilege to be involved in their children's school work and also allows the children to express their feelings, needs, and demands without any threat may have influenced the outcome of this study. This finding is in line with the findings of the study conducted by Odongo et al. (2016), which revealed that an authoritative parenting style tends to result in children who are happy, capable, and successful in maintaining peaceful relationships. This finding conforms to that of Femi (2018), who found that students from authoritative homes are most likely to perform better academically than children from autocratic parents.

The analysis of data on research question two and hypothesis two revealed a moderately negative and insignificant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and school adjustment of junior secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area. This may be due to the fact that authoritarian parents do not create a conducive environment for their children to express their feelings about issues that bother them. Getting parental attention in an authoritarian home is always difficult since such homes are plagued with threats. Children who grow up in such an environment may also find it very difficult to adjust in school, especially at the junior secondary school level. This finding is in line with the findings of the study conducted by Njoku and Akaninwor-David (2019), which revealed that authoritarian parenting style had a significant higher prediction of inadequate social adjustment on the part of the students. This finding is also in tandem with that of Adegboyega et al. (2021), which revealed authoritarian parenting has a negative influence on students' social adjustment in secondary schools.

The analysis of data on research question three and hypothesis three also revealed a moderately negative and insignificant relationship between permissive parenting and the academic adjustment of public secondary one students in Etche Local Government Area. This result is not surprising because if parents show no adequate concern for their children's well-being, the children, on their own, may be very lackadaisical about their school adjustment. To them, they can do whatever they like in school since their parents will not bother asking them how they are faring in school. Some of those children may stay away from school for several weeks or even months without any justifiable reason. This present finding lends credence to Seth and Emmanuel (2018), who earlier found a significant difference in adolescents' social adjustment based on permissive parents homes. The authors added that in permissive homes, children are not properly nurtured in moral attitudes and habits, and they are not always cautioned when they go wrong. They and their parents tend to live a

carefree life, which is detrimental to social adjustment. Njoku and Akaninwor-David (2019) added that permissive parenting is the main cause of disruptive behaviours among students in public secondary schools. Hence, it is believed that students who exhibit disruptive behaviours may have problems with academic adjustment.

Conclusion / Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that parenting styles (authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive) are important determinants of school adjustment of students. Thus, it is important to pay close attention to parenting styles in order to ensure that students are well adjusted in school. School adjustment is very necessary for enhancing social relationships and achieving maximum academic productivity among students.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should adopt an authoritative parenting style more in training their children so that they can establish peaceful relationships and display conduct that will help them in their school adjustment.
2. Parents should adopt a moderate use of authoritarian parenting style in training their children, since it does not help students much in achieving school adjustment.
3. Parents should refrain from living a carefree life and display more socially acceptable behaviours that can contribute to their children's overall adjustment.

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